

The Dowry in Mid-Nineteenth-Century Papal States: The Case of Umbellina Livi

Sara Delmedico

Abstract: The dowry played a key role in nineteenth-century Papal States. It was the only inheritance right of a woman, and crucial to obtain a good marriage; therefore, its amount was to be carefully valued. As we shall see, the law ruled that a dowry was to be “appropriate”. This notion of “appropriateness” had fluid boundaries and was often exploited by families to the detriment of women. Through a close analysis of a judicial case reported in the legal journal *Giornale del foro*, I give an insight into mid-nineteenth-century society. The study of this dispute allows us to understand which issues the protagonists brought in to support their claims and around what their world revolved. By examining the instances that led to the final verdict we also understand how discord was tackled by courts and what was considered important to society. The picture that emerges is of a society still static and patriarchal, characterised by power relations and cultural expectations where wealth was pivotal. However, even though women were in a subordinate position, their voices did not go completely unheeded and, to some extent, their claims were taken into consideration.

Keywords: women, dowry, Papal States, wealth, discord, courts, nineteenth century.

Cessa inoltre nei padri medesimi il fomite di accumular sostanze, allorché sanno, che queste devono già pervenire col mezzo delle femmine ad altre ignote famiglie.¹

(The incitement to accumulate wealth ceases in the fathers, when they know, that these would arrive to other unknown families by means of females)

Accumulating wealth for daughters was meaningless. This idea was widely accepted by nineteenth-century fathers. As *patres* of large

¹ G.M. Negri, *Dei difetti del Codice Civile Italico, che porta il titolo di Codice Napoleone e dei pregi del Codice Civile Austriaco* (Vicenza: Parise, 1815), 76.

patriarchal families,² they were entrusted with the task of perpetuating the “splendor del loro cognome” (the splendour of their names) through physical symbols, such as a palace in the main street of their towns,³ and by instilling the sense of the *casato* (house) within the family. This family unit was a moral body, tightly bound by kinship links, with its own peculiarities and customs. Its prestige was deemed to be transmitted through the male line, and a prominent position was given to men, to whom preserving wealth was pivotal. Since the Middle Ages, the *casato* had relevance in law and society for its *substancia* (wealth, properties),⁴ and fathers were deemed not to have any motivation to accumulate and preserve their wealth if it risked being inherited by people not bearing their names. Excluding or limiting women’s access to the family’s wealth would serve this goal.

Nineteenth-century lawmakers reinforced the subaltern position of women in society by hindering their ability to obtain large portions of their fathers’ inheritance. In the Papal States, as in almost the entire Italian peninsula, a woman’s only right over their paternal inheritance was a dowry, which was to be *congrua* (appropriate).⁵

² In this context, the term *patres* has the meaning ‘male adults’, not subjected to any *potestas*. A *paterfamilias* was meant to be the chief of a family. On fathers’ authority, see M. Cavina, *Il padre spodestato: l’autorità paterna dall’antichità a oggi* (Rome: Laterza, 2007).

³ Negri, *Dei difetti del Codice Civile Italiano*, 76.

⁴ On this point, see Albericus of Rosate, *Dictionarium iuri tam civilis quam canonici* (Venice: [n. pub.], 1581), sub *Familia*. See also Bartolus of Saxoferrato, *Commentaria in primam infortiati* (Lyon: [n. pub.], 1552), 112.

⁵ A brief overview on the legal status of women in the Papal States can be found in S. Delmedico, *Breve studio sulla condizione giuridica della donna nello stato pontificio dell’Ottocento* ([n. p.]: [lulu.com], 2014). Several studies have been undertaken on various aspects of women’s history: in particular, see G. Duby and M. Perrot, *Storia delle donne, L’Ottocento* (Rome and Bari: Laterza, 1991); G. Calvi and I. Chabot, eds, *Le ricchezze delle donne: diritti patrimoniali e poteri familiari in Italia* (Turin: Rosenberg and Sellier, 1998); G. Bock, *Le donne nella storia europea. Dal Medioevo ai giorni nostri* (Rome: Laterza, 2001); A. Bravo et

This article aims to explain the idea of “appropriateness” through the analysis of a case reported in the *Giornale del Foro*, a journal of jurisprudence published in the Papal States.⁶ As we shall see, this concept had fluid boundaries, and was handled and exploited by courts and families to the detriment of women. The analysis of this case also outlines relevant differences between the inheritance portions of sons and daughters, and examines the criteria used to shape the concept of appropriateness.

Studies considering women before the law in the nineteenth-century Papal States are particularly thin on the ground. There is extensive research on this period yet to be done: this article provides a first step towards filling this gap. Indeed, my work tries to uncover some aspects of the law in action in the years between the Restoration and the Unification of Italy, that is from 1815 up to 1861, a very crucial period for the Italian peninsula, with the winds of the French Revolution still blowing, and new prerogatives and ideas in conflict with the reaction the reinstated monarchs wanted to ensure. In the first section of the article, I provide a brief overview of the law with regard to dowry. I then examine and contextualise the case reported in the *Giornale del foro*. I conclude my analysis by inferring the nature of the relationships that women and men had with the law.

Dowry, a woman’s only inheritance right

During the *Ancien Régime*, the legal system of the Papal States was

al., *Storia sociale delle donne nell’Italia contemporanea* (Rome: Laterza, 2001); S. Feci, *Pesci fuor d’acqua: donne a Roma in età moderna* (Rome: Viella, 2004).

⁶ The *Giornale del foro* was published from 1816 up to 1874 with several titles: *Raccolta delle più importanti decisioni dei Supremi Tribunali di Roma in materia contenziosa* (1816-1824); *Giornale del foro: raccolta delle decisioni e massime più importanti dei supremi tribunali di Roma in materia contenziosa* (1824-1833); *Giornale del foro ove si raccolgono le decisioni e massime più importanti dei supremi tribunali di Roma e dello Stato Pontificio in materia contenziosa* (1833-1839); and *Giornale del foro: in cui si raccolgono le più importanti regiodicate dei supremi tribunali di Roma e dello Stato Pontificio in materia civile* (1839-1874).

built upon several sources of law, such as municipal statutes, Roman law (for example, Emperor Justinian's *Corpus Iuris Civilis*), canon and customary law.⁷ It was a fragmentary framework with a considerable amount of norms, which often conflicted and overlapped. With regard to inheritance, women were allowed to only obtain a dowry from the patrimony of their fathers.⁸

Dowry was an ancient institution known since the second century BC.⁹ Once just a moral and social obligation, scholars generally accept that the dowry became a legal obligation in the sixth century.¹⁰ In the Early Middle Ages it lost importance and, especially in areas conquered by the Lombards, when they married, families used to provide daughters with the *faderfio*,¹¹ a negligible gift, the

⁷ For an overview on the law in force during the *Ancien Régime* and in the nineteenth century, see P. Grossi and L. Hooper, *A History of European Law* (Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010). See also A. Romano, *Famiglia, successioni e patrimonio familiare nell'Italia medievale e moderna* (Turin: Giappichelli, 1994). On the *Corpus Iuris Civilis*, see H. Kantorowicz and W.W. Buckland, *Studies in the Glossators of the Roman Law: Newly Discovered Writings of the Twelfth Century* (Cambridge: CUP, 1938). On municipal statutes, see F. Calasso, *Medio Evo del diritto* (Milan: Giuffrè, 1954). On canon law, see J. Gaudemet, *Le Droit canonique* (Paris: Fides, 1989); J. Gaudemet, *La Formation du droit canonique médiéval* (London: Variorum, 1980).

⁸ For an overview on dowry, see S. Delmedico, "The "Appropriateness" of Dowry: Women and Inheritance in the Papal States in the Early Nineteenth Century", *GLOSSAE. European Journal of Legal History* 13 (2016), 165-181 (168-71).

⁹ See C. Fayer, *La familia romana: aspetti giuridici ed antiquari*, 2 vols, II (Rome: "L'Erma" di Bretschneider, 1994), 673.

¹⁰ A further discussion on this point can be found in Fayer, *La familia romana*, 673, 717-37.

¹¹ On the *faderfio*, see F. Criscuolo, *La donna nella storia del diritto privato italiano* (Palermo: Caronna and Macoclin, 1885), 49-50; see also M. Bellomo, *Ricerche sui rapporti patrimoniali tra coniugi* (Milan: Giuffrè, 1960), 61-63; M. Bellomo, "Dote (diritto intermedio)", *Enciclopedia del diritto*, 16 vols, XIV (Milan: Giuffrè, 1958-1965), 9. Enrico Galluppi, in his *La successione dei coniugi nella storia interna del diritto italiano* (1873), claimed that the *faderfio* was just composed of dress, see E. Galluppi, *La successione dei coniugi nella storia interna del diritto italiano* (Rome: Civelli, 1873), 58. At the time of the Lombards, a

value of which increased over the years. The rediscovery of the *Corpus Iuris Civilis* of Justinian in the twelfth century also led to a revival of the Roman dowry. In that period, the value of the *faderfio* was close to that of the Roman dowry. However, families turned to provide the latter, particularly because it allowed them to register a mortgage over the goods of those who received the dowry. Securing the dowry was crucial, as this usually was a woman's sole patrimony, and, on the dowry, she had to rely at the time of her widowhood. The dowry also began to be considered a daughter's rightful share of paternal inheritance, and this custom gained force of law by being included in municipal statutes.¹² Women were therefore excluded

husband acquired also a right of guardianship over his wife known as *mundium*. Alongside the guardianship, a husband acquired the right over her properties. The *mundium* also implied that a husband was obliged to protect his wife and was responsible for her. See E. Southon, *Marriage, Sex and Death: The Family and the Fall of the Roman West* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2017), 34-37. On the *mundium*, see also F. Brandileone, *Saggi sulla storia della celebrazione del matrimonio in Italia* (Milan: Hoepli, 1906), 4-9; E. Cortese, "Per la storia del mundio in Italia", *Rivista italiana per le scienze giuridiche* 3/9-10 (1955-1956), 323-474.

¹² Bellomo, *Ricerche sui rapporti patrimoniali tra coniugi*, 163-84. A number of studies dealt with the subject of dowry during the Middle Ages up to the Late Renaissance, see Bellomo, "Dote (diritto intermedio)", *Enciclopedia del diritto*, 8-32; J. Goody, J. Thirsk and E.P. Thompson, eds, *Family and Inheritance - Rural Society in Western Europe, 1200-1800* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1979); M.A. Kaplan (ed.), *The Marriage Bargain: Women and Dowries in European History* (New York: Haworth Press, 1985); T. Kuehn, *Law, Family and Women: Toward a Legal Anthropology of Renaissance Italy* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1991); T. Dean, 'Fathers and Daughters: Marriage Laws and Marriage Disputes in Bologna and Italy, 1200-1500', T. Dean and K.J.P. Lowe, eds, *Crime, Society and the Law in Renaissance Italy* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994), 85-106; M. Bellomo, *La condizione giuridica della donna in Italia. Vicende antiche e moderne* (Rome: Il Cigno, 1996); J. Goody, "Dowry and the Rights of Women to Property", in C.M. Hann (ed.), *Property Relations: Renewing the Anthropological Tradition* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998), 201-13; J. Kirshner, *Marriage, Dowry, and Citizenship in Late Medieval and Renaissance Italy* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2015).

propter dotem (because of the dowry).

The value of dowries underwent a significant inflation during the Renaissance as it was a means to show a family's prestige. Lawmakers responded with laws limiting the amount of money or goods which could be given as a dowry.¹³ At the turn of the seventeenth century, dowries returned to being "appropriate" to the families' status or equal to the *legitima portio*.¹⁴

With Napoleon's conquests, the *Codice Civile pel Regno d'Italia*, the translated version of *Code Civil des Français*, was applied to the Italian peninsula by a decree of 30th March 1806, and was meant to be the sole source of law.¹⁵ Amongst its many provisions, the code directed that children could inherit from their parents regardless of their gender, and, therefore, the dowry was just an advance on the family's patrimony.¹⁶

After the Congress of Vienna, the restored monarchs reinstated the law of the *Ancien Régime*. This meant that Roman, canon and customary laws were reinforced, and daughters were again excluded by law *propter dotem*.

In the Papal States, shortly after his return to power, on 6 July 1816, Pope Pius VII (1800-1823) introduced several civil law reforms with the *Moto proprio della Santità di Nostro Signore papa*

¹³ A. Pertile, *Storia del diritto italiano: dalla caduta dell'Impero Romano alla codificazione*, 7 vols, III (Turin: Unione tipografico-editrice, 1892), 322.

¹⁴ The *legitima portio* was the portion of a testator's estates that could not be bequeathed by will. Its amount was to be calculated according to Novel 18.1 of Justinian's *Novellae Constitutiones*. The *legitima portio* was a third of the deceased's estate, if there were four or fewer children, and a half if there were more than four children.

¹⁵ The *Code Civil des Français*, generally known as Code Napoléon, was promulgated on 21 March 1804. Its Italian translation, the *Codice Civile pel Regno d'Italia*, unified the legal *régime* of the entire peninsula, with the exception of some areas such as Sicily, Sardinia and some territories of the Venetia. See also "Decreto di promulgazione", 16 January 1806, *Codice civile di Napoleone il grande pel Regno d'Italia* (Milan: Reale Stamperia, 1807), 687.

¹⁶ Art. 745, *Codice Civile del Regno d'Italia*, 43.

Pio VII sull'organizzazione dell'amministrazione pubblica. According to Article 113 of this act, women were to be provided with an appropriate dowry, which was to be equal to the *legitima portio*, its amount based on Roman law.¹⁷ Even though, this article was intended to apply only to those not yet dowered at the time of their father's death, it allowed women to have a precisely quantifiable dowry over their paternal inheritance.

With the *Moto Proprio* concerning the reform of public administration issued by Pope Leo XII (1823-1829) on 5 October 1824, dowries provided after the father's death did not need to be equal to the *legitima portio* anymore.¹⁸ This meant that sons were again allowed to provide their sisters just with "appropriate" dowries. The value of the dowry returned to be extremely flexible, as it was calculated according to several criteria such as status and customs. For example, a dowry, even extremely scant, could be considered appropriate without any further appraisal if a woman married a man of her social class.¹⁹ This provision was also confirmed by the following *Moto Proprio* of Pope Leo XII (1827), and in the *Regolamento Legislativo e Giudiziario per gli affari civili*, enacted by Pope Gregory XVI (1831-1846) in 1834.²⁰

Despite the Enlightenment and the French revolution introducing new ideas and sentiments, nineteenth-century Italian society was still strictly categorised by class, and status was very important. In such a world, families played a crucial role. They were

¹⁷ Art. 113, *Moto proprio della Santità di Nostro Signore papa Pio VII in data de' 6 luglio 1816 sull'organizzazione dell'amministrazione pubblica* (Rome: Baret, 1816), 47.

¹⁸ Art. 117, Tit. IV, *Moto proprio della Santità di Nostro Signore Papa Leone XII in data dei 5 ottobre 1824 sulla riforma dell'amministrazione pubblica della procedura civile e delle tasse dei giudizi* (Rome: Poggioli, 1824), 22.

¹⁹ Art. 116, Tit. IV, *Moto proprio* (1824), 22.

²⁰ See Art. 128, *Moto proprio della santità di nostro Signore Papa Leone XII sulla amministrazione pubblica del 21 dicembre 1827* (Rome: R.C.A., 1827), XVII, and Art. 19, *Regolamento Legislativo e Giudiziario per gli affari civili* (Rome: R.C.A., 1834), 13.

male-led “micro-monarchies”, with a patriarchal structure and their own hierarchies and customs.²¹ To families, the marriage of their female members was very important: it created alliances, which could increase the *casato*’s prestige, and implied a devolution of wealth by means of the dowry. As I shall outline in the next section, this transfer of goods was not a smooth process and could lead to several disputes.

Challenging male authority

The case I will consider in this article is a lawsuit initiated by Umbellina Livi in 1842. She was the daughter of Francesco Livi, an official of both the Apostolic Datary and the Apostolic Chancery, two offices of the Roman Curia. His town of origin was Albano, near the capital city of the Papal States, but he lived in Rome with his family. He had two sons and four daughters.²² They were a family *di civile condizione* (they were not noble but they enjoyed a comfortable socio-economic status). One of his daughters became a nun,²³ and

²¹ With regard to family, see, in particular, J. Goody, *The Development of the Family and Marriage in Europe* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983); M. Barbagli, *Sotto lo stesso tetto. Mutamenti della famiglia in Italia dal XV al XX secolo* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 1984); P. Melograni and L. Scaraffia, eds, *La famiglia italiana dall’Ottocento a oggi* (Rome and Bari: Laterza, 1988); M. Barbagli and D.I. Kertzer, eds, *Storia della famiglia italiana, 1750-1950* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 1992); T. Dean and K.J.P. Lowe, eds, *Marriage in Italy, 1300-1650* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998); G. Vecchio, *Profilo storico della famiglia: la famiglia italiana tra Ottocento e Novecento* (Cinisello Balsamo: San Paolo, 1999); P. Ungari, *Storia del diritto di famiglia in Italia (1796-1975)* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2002); I. Porciani (ed.), *Famiglia e nazione nel lungo Ottocento italiano: modelli, strategie, reti di relazioni* (Rome: Viella, 2006); D. Lombardi, *Storia del matrimonio dal Medioevo a oggi* (Bologna: Il Mulino, 2008).

²² *Giornale del foro* 2 (1842), 175-79.

²³ On this point, see G. Vismara, *L’unità della famiglia nella storia del diritto in Italia* (Rome: Apollinaris, 1956), 259-61; Ungari, *Storia del diritto di famiglia*, 57. The jurist Giovanni Battista De Luca explained that if a prince wanted to marry his daughter, he had to provide a 100,000-*scudo* dowry, whereas, if she became a nun, a dowry worth 1,000 *scudi*, or even less, would be enough. See, G.B. De Luca, *Il*

another obtained a 742-*scudo* dowry from her father. Shortly before dying, Francesco inherited extensive land in the countryside and close to the town of Albano from his brother Giuseppe, which considerably increased the value of his patrimony.

After his death, in 1831, one of his daughters married, and her brothers gave her a 1,000-*scudo* dowry and furniture. The fourth daughter, Umbellina, was unmarried and asked for her dowry based upon Article 22 of the 1834 *Regolamento Legislativo e Giudiziario per gli affari civili*.²⁴ Upon this article, once one attained the age of 25, a woman was entitled to demand and obtain her dowry even if she was not going to marry. Her brothers gave her two estates in the town of Albano, which they said were worth 1,000 *scudi*. Umbellina was not content, and initiated a lawsuit before the tribunal of the *Auditor Camerae*,²⁵ which appointed an expert to assess the exact

dottor volgare, ovvero Il compendio di tutta la legge civile, canonica, feudale e municipale, nelle cose più ricevute in pratica, moralizzato in lingua italiana, 6 vols, III ([n.p.]: [n.pub.], 1673), 111. The jurist and historian Ludovico Muratori tackled this issue, too, and pointed out that providing a dowry was an enormous commitment for a family; therefore, many girls were sent to monasteries and deemed to lead deprived lives if becoming nuns was not their choice. See, L.A. Muratori, *Della pubblica felicità, oggetto de' buoni principi* (Lucca: [n.pub.], 1749), 279.

²⁴ Art. 22, *Regolamento Legislativo e Giudiziario per gli affari civili*, 13.

²⁵ The *Auditor Camerae* was a judge with jurisdiction over civil and criminal matters. The tribunal of the *Reverenda Camera Apostolica*, quoted in legal records as “tribunal of the A.C.”, could rule over cases on first instance regarding the area of Rome and its province, and as court of appeal for the entirety of the Papal States. The A.C. was also the competent tribunal for clergymen, and for people employed by the Curia. See, E. Lodolini, “L’amministrazione periferica e locale nello Stato pontificio dopo la Restaurazione”, *Ferrara viva* 1 (1959), 5-32, and “L’ordinamento giudiziario civile e penale nello Stato Pontificio (sec. XIX)”, *Ferrara viva* 2 (1959), 43-73; M. Mombelli Castracane, *La codificazione civile nello Stato Pontificio* (Naples: Edizioni scientifiche italiane, 1988); I. Fosi, “Il governo della giustizia nello Stato Pontificio in età moderna”, in A. Giorgi, S. Moscadelli and C. Zarrilli, *La documentazione degli organi giudiziari nell’Italia tardo-medievale e moderna: atti del Convegno di studi, Siena, Archivio di Stato*,

value of the estates.²⁶

The brothers, then, appealed to the *Sacra Rota*.²⁷ Their lawyer claimed that Francesco had died when the *Moto Proprio* of Pope Leo XII was still in force, and this excluded women *propter masculos* (because of males) and not *propter dotem*. Therefore, the value of the dowry was not related to the *legitima portio*. This was also true in the case of the daughter being unmarried at the time of her father's death, and, the lawyer argued, Umbellina was to be excluded from inheriting. The lawyer also claimed that the inquiry into the value of Francesco's patrimony was irrelevant because Umbellina was entitled to receive a *congrua* dowry only, which was in no way related to the patrimony, and was already being given by her brothers.

Moreover, Umbellina's dowry was higher than the precedent set in her family: both her mother and her grandmother had received a dowry worth 500 *scudi*, and her sisters had received a dowry worth less than 1,000 *scudi*. Furthermore, the lawyer added that the inventory of Giuseppe's inheritance showed that his patrimony was worth 10,000 *scudi*, and Francesco's wealth was almost all constituted by his brother's bequest. This meant that the increase in the value of his patrimony was not yet deemed to have had an impact on the family's status.

Umbellina's lawyer argued that, based on Pope Leo's *Moto Proprio*, a dowry was not to be equal to the *legitima portio* but should be a sum close to that amount. He added that Francesco's patrimony

15-17 settembre 2008 (Rome: Ministero per i beni e le attività culturali, 2012), 625-50.

²⁶ *Giornale del foro* 2 (1842), 176.

²⁷ On the tribunal of the *Sacra Rota* or *Ruota*, see D. Bernini, *Il tribunale della S. Rota Romana* (Rome: Bernabò, 1717); K. Salonen, *Papal Justice in the Late Middle Ages: The Sacra Romana Rota* (London: Routledge, 2016). Its competences were broadened with the several *Moto proprio* of the nineteenth century, see, Art. 35, *Moto proprio ... (1816)*, 42; Artt. 33 and 37, *Moto proprio ... (1824)*, 19. For an overview, see Lodolini, "L'ordinamento giudiziario civile e penale nello Stato Pontificio (sec. XIX)", 46.

was worth 35,000 *scudi* and not 10,000 as the brothers maintained. Therefore, Umbellina's dowry was not *congrua*, both for its amount and the *qualità dei fondi che dicevansi deteriori fra tutti gli altri del patrimonio* (the quality of lands, the value of which was estimated to be the lowest among the entire patrimony).²⁸

Further, her dowry could not be calculated on the basis of the family's customs alone, because the *gius commune* provided that it was to be the result of *più dati tutti unitamente ponderati* (several data, all to be weighted together): the amount of the patrimony, their status, the number of children, the custom of the family, the custom of the area where they lived, the dowries given by the father to the other daughters.²⁹

In this specific case, the amount of the dowry was to be decided by considering Francesco's patrimony, which had increased substantially after he inherited from his brother, and should not consider the sum given to Umbellina's sisters. Umbellina's lawyer suggested that a 4,000-*scudo* dowry was appropriate for her.

With a decision dated 8 April 1842, the *Sacra Rota* conceded that, *quantunque in simili casi non debba indagarsi sottilmente l'asse ereditario* (even though in these cases a meticulous investigation over the inherited patrimony is not needed), the *Livis* could not find any agreement on the value of their father's patrimony, and ordered that a technical appraisal on the patrimony was to be done.³⁰

The *Livi* brothers, too, appointed an expert of their choice, who maintained that Francesco's patrimony was worth 5,818.12.5 *scudi*. The court's technical experts, instead, appraised it as worth 34,307.75 *scudi*, more than six times the value Umbellina's brothers had pretended.

As a consequence of this appraisal, the *Sacra Rota* ordered Umbellina's brothers to give her 2,000 *scudi* as a dowry, but the

²⁸ *Giornale del Foro* 2 (1842), 177.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 178.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, 179.

brothers appealed this decision, and, in 1852, the Livi family was again before the tribunal to assess their litigation. The *Giornale del foro* highlighted that, in this case, *andò per le spese una somma molto maggiore della controversa, come sempre accade in tali giudizj* (as always happens in these cases, a sum much higher than the contested amount was spent for legal fees), and that the brothers had no consistent reason to oppose a 2,000-*scudo* dowry.³¹

The decision was once again confirmed. Indeed, the *Sacra Rota* argued that the appropriateness of a dowry was to be assessed by taking into account the strength of the patrimony, how many children there were in a family, and its status. By considering these factors, the prudent discretion of a judge could revise the dowry *nella misura della legittima, ed in somma anche minore, tale però che possa alla donna procurare nozze eguali e decorose* (as equal to the legitime, or even lower, given that its amount is such to allow a woman to obtain an honourable marriage to a person of similar status).³²

Moreover, the court argued that the custom of Albano to give women of similar status dowries not higher than 1,000 *scudi* was not applicable to this case. Indeed, to support their argument, Umbellina's brothers had brought in several documents to give evidence of the custom of their town of origin, but these referred to women who had received their dowries from their fathers and not from their brothers. A father was allowed to punish his daughter by giving her only alimony, but his heirs did not have such power.³³

Furthermore, the *Sacra Rota* argued that, although Albano was their town of origin, the Livis lived in Rome. The sum to be given

³¹ *Giornale del Foro ossia Raccolta di regudicate romane e straniere* 2 (1853), 167.

³² *Ibid.*, 168.

³³ Such a punishment could be made if a daughter's behaviour was deemed to be unworthy to her status, for example by compromising her modesty with a servant. See the case described in Delmedico, *Breve studio sulla condizione giuridica della donna nello stato pontificio dell'Ottocento*, 54-55.

as a dowry therefore had to consider the customs of the capital city, because there the Livi daughters were educated. Umbellina's two married sisters had received smaller dowries, but their circumstances were different: the first obtained a 742-*scudo* dowry from her father in 1823, before Francesco Livi had inherited from his brother Giuseppe, and the second received 1,000 *scudi* from her brothers which she claimed was just an advance, and began a separate lawsuit to obtain more money.

Marriage, dowry and the Italian society

Marriage was the pivotal institution of nineteenth-century Italian society. To a woman, it meant being considered worthy of respect as an active member of a family, while spinsterhood had to be avoided as, often, it also implied solitude and economic constraints.³⁴ Therefore, a good dowry made a woman attractive in the marriage market.

After the Restoration, the law regarding marriage and inheritance was similar along the Italian peninsula, with the exception of the Duchy of Parma, Piacenza and Guastalla, and the Kingdoms of the Two Sicilies and Lombardy-Venetia, in which the constitution of dowry was admitted but was just considered as an advance on paternal inheritance.³⁵

In the other states of the Italian peninsula, children were not allowed to inherit equally from their parents: sons prevailed over daughters, and the latter were to be content with a just dowry. As I outlined earlier, in the Papal States, the constitution of the dowry was regulated through the Pope's *Moto Proprio*, which, in 1816, directed that the dowry given by the deceased's heirs was to be equal to the

³⁴ On this point, see also S. Delmedico, "Alimenti e dote alla periferia dello Stato Pontificio: la famiglia Pucci", *The Italianist* 37, 1 (2017), 50-68 (50).

³⁵ See Art. 837, *Codice civile per gli stati parmensi*, Art. 667, *Codice per lo Regno delle Due Sicilie and Artt. 730-734, Codice civile universale austriaco pel Regno Lombardo-Veneto*, in *Collezione Completa dei Moderni Codici Civili* (Turin: Minerva Subalpina, 1845), 422, 274 and 187.

legitima portio. This norm was then withdrawn a few years later, in 1824, and, once again, the dowry became “appropriate”. In such a context, women’s rightful share of the paternal inheritance was quite negligible, and judges rarely assigned more money than that already given by the family. In the Livi case, despite the court doubling its amount, the dowry was still far from being equal even to the legitime. Indeed, Umbellina received 2,000 *scudi*, and her two brothers inherited roughly 15,000 *scudi* each. Nonetheless, they resisted giving their sister more than 1,000 *scudi*.

Alongside the specific legal issues, the case examined reveals interesting dynamics among families, such as the pattern of the family members’ thoughts and the way they understand their roles within society. If the behaviour of Umbellina’s brothers, who persistently appealed the tribunals’ decision in the hope that the final verdicts would be in their favour, testifies to their inability to accept challenges to their authority, her recurrent approaches to the courts are a clear sign that she was aware of the law and wanted her rights to be enforced. Umbellina knew that a good dowry was crucial to obtain a good marriage, and, for this reason, its amount was to be carefully valued. Not content with the dowry constituted by her brothers, Umbellina disputed its value, and also questioned what society expected from them, that is being weak-headed, obedient and prone to male authority.

The nineteenth century was a period of great change. The Risorgimento, the rise of the bourgeoisie, the first steps towards industrialisation, together with new ideas and ambitions, led to a redefinition of socio-cultural dynamics within Italian society. These changes also affected relations within the household, and tentatively challenged how authority was perceived. The case analysed in this study also testifies to this new consciousness. Umbellina’s behaviour, indeed, shows an active female subjectivity, which spoke outside of the boundaries established by society for women, and asked for her few rights to be enforced.

The law regarding dowry remained unchanged until 1865.

With the Unification of Italy, the *Civil Code of the Kingdom of Italy*, known as the Pisanelli code, permitted all children to succeed their parents regardless of their gender. Even though the constitution of dowry was still possible, it was just considered as an advance on parental inheritance. This code, however, did not introduce other substantial novelties. It reaffirmed, instead, the subaltern position of women through marital authorisation and the obedience/protection dichotomy within marriage.³⁶

³⁶ See, for example, Articles 131 and 132 of the Civil Code of the Kingdom of Italy, *Codice civile del regno d'Italia* (Turin: Stamperia Reale, 1865), 35.